

Hymenoptera

- p.1 1 Intro – Plesiomorphy in Neoptera, sclerites of humeral plate not fused
- p.2 2 Retention of Paleozoic leg segment pattern in Recent insects — Xyelidae
- p.3 Argidae (Blasticotomidae)_Runaria_reducta_FW+HW
- p.4 Braconidae_genus_undet_FW+HW
- p.5 Megalodontesidae_Tristactoides_lacourti_FW_base
- p.6 Orusidae_Griglia_sericata_FW
- p.7 Pamphiliidae, Pamphilius sp, HW
- p.8 Pamphiliidae_Pamphilius_amplectus_FW_base
- p.9 Pamphiliidae_Pamphilius_amplectus_FW+HW
- p.10 Pamphiliidae_Pamphilius_sp_FW+HW 1
- p.11 Pamphiliidae_Pamphilius_sp_FW+HW
- p.12 Pergidae, Perga_glabra_HW
- p.13 Pergidae_Perga_dorsalis_FW+HW
- p.14 Pergidae_Perga_dorsalis_Leach_FW+HW_Australia
- p.15 Pergidae_Perga_dorsalis_Leach_FW_base
- p.16 Siricidae, Sirex sp FW & FW
- p.17 Sphecidae, genus+sp._undet._FW+HW
- p.18 Sphecidae?_FW+HW
- p.19 Tenthredinidae, Tremex colomba, FW
- p.20 Tenthredinidae, Tremex colomba, HW
- p.21 Tenthredinidae_Tremex_colomba_FW_base_Canada
- p.22 Tenthredinidae_Tremex_colomba_HW_base_Canada
- p.23 Thynnidae_Tremex_columba_FW_base
- p.24 Thynnidae_genus_undet._FW
- p.25 Thynnidae_undet._genus_FW+HW
- p.26 Vespidae_Polistes_schach_FW+details
- p.27 Xyelidae Pleroneura sp, FW base 2
- p.28 Xyelidae FW & HW_02
- p.29 Xyelidae, Macroxyela, feruginea_FW_base
- p.30 Xyelidae, Macroxyela_feruginea_HW_base
- p.31 Xyelidae, Pleroneura bruneicornis FW & HW
- p.32 Xyelidae, Pleroneura bruneicornis HW _06
- p.33 Xyelidae, Pleuroneura_sp_FW_Base
- p.34 Xyelidae, Pleuroneura_sp_HW_Base
- p.35 Xyelidae, Xyelecia nearctica Ross_FW+HW
- p.36 Xyelidae, Xyelecia nearctica Ross_HW_Base
- p.37 Xyelidae, Xyelecia nearctica_Ross_FW_Base
- p.38 Xyelidae_Macroxyela_feruginea_FW+HW
- p.39 Xyelidae_fossil_Archexyela_crosbyi_Riek_1955_FW_Triassic_Qld_Australia

Xyelidae: Pleroneura sp., FW

The only wing in Neoptera known to me to have sclerites forming humeral plate not fused together into a single plate (plesiomorphy) 1

Retention of the Paleozoic leg segmentation pattern in Recent insects.

Recent sawflies are the only known Recent group of insects in which all original Pterygote leg segments including claws are still retained on their maxillary palps.

Blasticotomidae, *Runaria reducta*, FW & HW

Braconidae, genus undet, FW & HW

Megalodontidae: *Tristactoides lacourti* FW base

Orusidae, *Griglia sericata*, FW

ScP fused under R & MA

Pamphiliidae, *Pamphilius amplexus*, FW

Note: three plesiomorphies!
 Humeral plate shows composition of four sclerites:
 F=fulcrum of PC and of C
 B=basiventral of PC and C
 3 sclerites not fused to tergum

Pamphiliidae: *Pamphilius amplexus*, FW & HW

Pamphiliidae, *Pamphilius* sp. FW & HW

Rare plesiomorphy: in FW short stem of Cu and free base of CuA joining MP is not reduced

Pamphiliidae: *Pamphilius* sp.,

(black) FW & HW

CuA base reduced CuP reduced

HW

Pamphiliidae: *Pamphilius* sp.

Pergidae, *Perga dorsalis*, FW & HW

Plesiomorphy: CuA base not completely reduced

Pergidae: *Perga dorsalis* Leach, FW base

Perga shows ^(well the) important hymenopteran plesiomorphies:

- ① stem of M is absent
- ② stem of Cu is extremely short, CuA fuses to MP

Pergidae: *Perga dorsalis* Leach, FW & HW; Australia, Sydney Museum

Pergidae: *Perga glabra*, HW

Rare plesiomorphy:
CuP is not completely reduced
Note reduced ScP-

Siricidae

Sirex sp., FW, South Africa, female

Sirex sp., FW, Europe, common pest

Sphecidae, genus and sp. undet., FW & HW

Sphecidae? FW & HW; violet-blue metallic wings

FW Tenthredinidae: *Trimex Colomba* Drury Ottawa, Gatineau

Tenthredinidae, *Trimex colomba*, HW base, Canada

HW Tenthredinidae: Trimex Colomba

Thinnidae, undet genus. FW base

Thynnidae, genus undet., FW J. Evans colln, Sydney, Aust.

Thinnidae, undet genus. FW & HW

Vespidae, *Polistes schach*, FW and details

VENTRAL VIEW

FW Xyelidae: *Pleroneura* sp.

another sp. for comparison! Compare with the other figured specimen!

FM = the bend-down part of BH + BCu??
 Flcu lost
 FAJ - oblique, flat, not a roll! (Roll in *Neur. + Mecop*)
 goblet & plate not connected (ant) (bent)

R base very weakened (Hyn, autap.)
 turned upright

BR - BSc separated by ant

Hymenoptera: Xyelidae

Hymenoptera venation shows four long fusions: the usual long fusion of MA to R and RP; the supporting struts arcus and medial bridge expressed as long fusions, of MP to CuA and of RP&MA to MP; and the first cubital branch CuA 1+2 appears to be fused at length to MP 3+4. In the hind wing these highly derived characters are combined with several plesiomorphies. Claval line is not shortened, ends on the posterior margin, and is sometimes still marked by a weak indentation in the posterior wing margin. AA 1+2 and AA 3+4 are still strong independent veins that occupy a relatively large area. Hence, forming of the partial anojugal lobe is less advanced than in the related neopteran orders.

Xyelidae; fossil; *Archexyela crosbyi* Riek, 1955; FW; Triassic, Queensland, Aust.

Reconstruction of ancestral FW based on three fragments
 R & MA & MP basally adjacent
 CuA base present!
 AA 3+4 base plesiomorphic

Xyelidae, *Macroxyela ferruginea*, FW & HW

Xyelidae, *Macroxyela feruginea*, HW base

Fulcalaria F-M, F-Cu (=medial plate)
and possibly also F-A are reduced

Xyelidae, *Macroxyela feruginea*, FW

Plesiomorphies:
 humeral plate = F & B
 CuP partly retained
 Fulcalare F-Cu present
 F-A and F-J possibly present

Xyelidae: *Pleroneura*

In HW, anal lobe starts at anal fold! (as in *Hemiptera* and *Blattellomorpha* *Enderostoma*)

Hymenoptera: *Xyelidae*

possibly, MP₃₊₄ fuses with CuA₁₊₂....

Xyleidae, *Pleuroneura* sp., FW base, (see other species for variability)

Humeral plate includes F-PC & F-C and BPC & B-C
 Note: fulcraria F-M and FCu (medial plate) are reduced

Xyelidae, *Pleuroneura* sp., HW base

Fulcalare F-M and F-Cu reduced

Xyelidae, *Xyelecia nearctica* Ross, FW & HW

Xyelidae, *Xyelecia nearctica* Ross, HW base

Fulcaralia F-M, F-Cu, F-A are reduced Cubital axalare: AX-Cu is subdivided

Xyelidae, *Xyelecia nearctica* Ross, FW base

